

A roadmap for the standardization and harmonization of the Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification systems for Carbon Farming in Europe: challenges and pathways for data exchange, towards an EU-level harmonized system (D3.1).

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Project CREDIBLE: “Building momentum and trust to achieve credible soil carbon farming in the EU”.

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Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
CONTRIBUTING PARTNERS	6
LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATION	7
1. INTRODUCTION	8
2. METHODOLOGY	9
3. KEY DISCUSSION POINTS	11
3.1 Standardisation and harmonisation of data used in the carbon farming systems	11
3.2 Enabling soil data sharing.	16
4. ROADMAP OF SOLUTIONS	17
4.1 Inventory of existing components for standardisation and harmonisation of soil data	17
4.1.1 Data Formats for Soil Information	17
4.1.2 Data Structures and Domain Models.....	19
4.1.3 Vocabularies and Controlled Terminologies	20
4.1.4 Ontologies and Formal Knowledge Representations	21
4.1.5 Conversion Tools and Harmonisation Pipelines	24
4.2 Results of the session at the carbon farming summit 19th March 2026 in Padua.	25
4.2.1 Session contents:	25
4.2.1 Session results	29
4.3 Barriers and incentives for sharing input-data needed in carbon farming and MRV systems in Europe	41
5 CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS	43
6 REFERENCES	44

Executive summary

Purpose

This present report summarises the results of the activities undertaken by the Focus Group 3.1, *How to harmonise public and private datasets for mapping and monitoring soil carbon dynamics*, of the Project Credible. During 2 years and a half of activity (winter 2023 – spring 2026), the focus group has discussed the topic of balancing the need for accuracy –towards high value carbon credits– and the need for sustainable and affordable costs of certification systems, and the specific role played by incentivising data sharing among public and private actors involved. Active members of the Focus Group belong both to the public and private sector, and both to research and to farm-advisory certification bodies.

Intended audience:

The intended audience is a wide range of stakeholders involved in Monitoring Reporting and Verification systems of carbon farming, ranging from research and academia, intermediaries (advisory and extension services, certifiers, consultancy, service providers), information technology support (including Monitoring Reporting and Verification technologies, remote sensing, and modelling), supply chain actor (input and output), carbon project developer, farmers and farmers union, credit buyers and project funders, regulators and policymakers, public authorities, standardisation bodies, standardisation and harmonisation initiatives and projects, other public entities.

Description of the main activities: The focus group has met regularly with monthly meetings, seldomly inviting external speakers; has organised 2 breakout session at 2 carbon farming summits, the first in Valencia (2023), and the 3rd in Padua (2025), and has contributed to the organisation of a session at the second carbon farming summit in Dublin (2024), organised by the focus group 3.4 *How to use data from long-term monitoring sites in the context of carbon farming?*, with which has strictly collaborated. Has performed an open consultation and elaborated a milestone: “Barriers and incentives for sharing input-data needed in carbon farming and MRV systems in Europe”
<https://zenodo.org/records/15404523>.

Key results:

- **Standardising/harmonising MRV for higher value carbon credits:** A wide range of stakeholders, not only from research and academia, but also from the private sector (farmers, supply-chain actors, farm advisory and extension services, certifiers, consultancy, service provider), information technology support, agreed that *a standardised/harmonised MRV systems could produce higher valuable/credible carbon credits*.
- **Towards a federated and mutual sharing of data between public and privates:** The mutual sharing of high quality standardised/harmonised datasets, between public and private actors involved in the carbon farming, would constitute a win-win condition, because it would enable the determination of reliable/accurate benchmark sites, of accurate and reliable standardised baselines and carbon sequestration potentials; it could improve the carbon modelling accuracies, and finally would produce cost-effective and accurate carbon credits, this could constitute an effective leverage and incentives for data sharing both from public and from privates’ stakeholders. The production of data is costly and time consuming, therefore, the sharing should be in all directions: privates to public, public to privates. The following principles are recognised as essential to promote data sharing: i) collecting data once and using them for multiple purposes; ii) confidentiality of personal data; iii) recognising data ownership; iv) defining and agreeing on the data re-use; v) giving a service back; vi) rewarding intellectual property rights. While a central storage is impracticable, what has demonstrated to be

achievable is a federated system in which datasets are permanently stored in repositories maintained by different institutions (e.g. zenodo, dataverse) and they are made findable through centralised and interlinked metadata catalogues/portals. As farm data –including georeferenced soil data– are recognised as personal data (Fantappiè et al., 2021), the confidentiality should be guaranteed by anonymisation/aggregation procedures, or by access/sharing with request procedures, which imply the signing of embedded contracts for data sharing with farmers. To incentivise private companies to share their data, the effort of data collection should in large part be subsidised with the support of the European Union. One farmer should have the ability to request a subsidy for data collection –such as soil sampling– and hire himself a company to perform both sampling and lab analysis.

○ **Adopt a common standard with optional validated harmonisation:** A large effort is still needed because the current carbon farming certification frameworks do not foresee standard data formats, data-model structures, and standard vocabularies. Recently European Commission has approved the Soil Monitoring Law which has set the legal base for the standards to be implemented to monitor some relevant soil descriptors, including soil organic carbon, bulk density and biodiversity. Those standards are mandatory, but the Member States can adopt different standards if they can demonstrate that a validated transfer function is available to convert to those standards, that is, if a harmonisation is possible. The stakeholders suggested to align policies, e.g. to adopt the soil monitoring law standards in the carbon farming certification framework. Capacity building and awareness raising should be financed with public funds, to facilitate and incentives the usage of such standards.

Research and practice implications: Although several data standardisation and harmonisation initiatives are ongoing, the results of the focus group activity underlined that they are almost yet unknown in the carbon farming sector. The information and technology behind the data infrastructure is still very difficult to be used by non-expert in informatics, therefore, a research effort is still needed to produce user-friendly application for standard data sharing, such as produced by the EJPSOIL project (the [EJP SOIL metadata catalogue](#), the INSPIRE compliant [Geopackage-soil](#), the [INSPIRE assimilation cookbook](#)) and under production by the Soilwise project (the [Soilwise metadata catalogue](#), the [Soil Geopackage](#), the [soil vocabulary](#), the [soil companion](#)), and

Policy implications: Alignment between legislation is needed: the recently adopted Soil Monitoring Law (SML) for Europe and the Carbon Certification Frameworks (CRCF) go in that direction, but they should be correlated, e.g. by adopting in the CRCF the standards foreseen for soils monitoring in the SML. Good examples of ongoing public support towards standardisation/harmonisation and data sharing are the General Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus of the European Environmental Agency, the European Soil Observatory of the Joint Research Center, the AGROVOC and GLOSI standard vocabularies produced and maintained by the FAO Global Soil Partnership (GSP), and the GSP initiatives GLOSOLAN, RECSOIL, and INSII. A federated system, supported by standardisation/harmonisation, could enable a cost-effective improvement of carbon certification systems world-wide. Collecting data is costly and time consuming, therefore, the whole system should envision the reducing of monitoring reporting and verification costs, so to enable credible and cost-effective carbon credits. The principle *collect once and use multiple times* should be at the base of the system. Efforts in capacity building and awareness raising are also needed with public support.

Conclusions:

A standardised/harmonised MRV systems could produce higher valuable/credible carbon credits. A federated data sharing system should be put in place based on the principle *collect once and use multiple times*, with common standard and optional validated harmonisation. Policy alignment and public support in capacity building on the topic of data standardisation and harmonisation is needed.

Contributing Partners

Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
Council for Agricultural Research and Economics	CREA	Italy
Hellenic Agriculture Organisation	ELGO	Greece
University of Luxemburg	UL	Luxemburg
Wageningen Research	WR	The Netherlands
Flanders research institute for agriculture, fisheries and food	ILVO	Belgium
Soil Capital	SC	Belgium
Polyor SAS	Polyor	France
eAgronom	eAgronom	Czech Republic
Datacove	Datacove	Austria
Aarhus University	AU	Denmark
Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement	INRAE	France

List of acronyms and abbreviation

CRCF, Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming

EU, European Union

EUSO, European Soil Observatory

FAIR, Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable

GHG, Green House Gas

INSPIRE, Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community

IT, Information Technology

JRC, Joint Research Center

MRV, Monitoring Reporting Verification

RS, Remote Sensing

SML, Soil Monitoring Law

URL, Uniform Resource Locator

VCM, Voluntary Carbon Market

1. Introduction

In order to have a coherent Monitoring Reporting and Verification system which could apply at different scales, from the field scale, to the reporting at national and international scale, there is the need for a standardization and harmonisation of procedures adopted at several levels, starting with procedures, instruments, and protocols adopted in field, passing through the analytical methods and standards adopted, the carbon modelling methods adopted, and finally on the base of the reporting procedure. Several data are needed, such as soil data, biomass input data, land use and management data, climatic data, land parcels data, possibly proximal and remote sensing data. Several technical, economic and legal challenges must be overcome to have comparable and coherent results. Numerous international research projects and other initiatives, both at national and international scale, are contributing to solve the issues related to standardisation and harmonisation of MRV systems, e.g. [JRC-EUSO](#), [EJPSOIL](#), [MARVIC](#), [MRV4SOC](#), [ICOS](#), [eLTER](#), [EUROSOLAN](#), [SOILWISE](#), [BONARES](#), [GOV4ALL](#) among others. Public entities and private stakeholders collaborate in these projects, since in MRV systems the private component is highly relevant. The EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Certification Framework aims at increasing stakeholders' faith in the Voluntary Carbon Market (VCM) through robust, cost-effective, and transparent Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) systems. Finding solutions to overcome legal and technical constraints for data sharing is a prerequisite to the determination of accurate and reliable "standardised baselines" which are requested to be used in the CRCF regulation.

The [Focus Group 3.1](#), *How to harmonise public and private datasets for mapping and monitoring soil carbon dynamics*, of the Project Credible has discussed, during 2 years and a half of activity, the topic of balancing the need for accuracy –towards high value carbon credits– and the need for sustainable and affordable costs of certification systems, and the specific role played by incentivising data sharing among public and private actors involved. Active members of the Focus Group belong both to the public and private sector, and both to research and to farm-advisory certification bodies.

Focus Group 3.1. has centered conversations around two main themes related to MRV systems: 1. harmonising soil analysis: standards and protocols, 2. enabling soil data sharing.

2. Methodology

This report is based on the feedback from main activities (table 2.1) of the focus group 3.1, whose participants are listed in table 2.2.

Table 2.1. Main FG3.1 activities from 2024-2025

Activity description	Date	Location
Inaugural Focus Group online meeting	20 th December 2023	online
Discussions with separate FG members	January-March 2023	online
Meetings concerning preparation for the European Carbon Farming Summit with FG representatives	January-March 2023	online
Plenary session presentation + panel during the European Carbon Farming Summit	6 th of March 2024	in presence
Breakout session during the European Carbon Farming Summit	6 th of March 2024	in presence
Post-summit discussions during several meetings	March 2024	online
Regular monthly meetings	November 2024 to February 2026	online
Open consultation	December 2024 – February 2025	online
Elaboration of the milestone “ Barriers and incentives for sharing input-data needed in carbon farming and MRV systems in Europe” https://zenodo.org/records/15404523	14 th May 2025	published on zenodo
Breakout session during the European Carbon Farming Summit	19 th March 2026	in presence

Table 2.2. *Participants of Focus Group 3.1*

Name				
Name	Role	Affiliation	Affiliation Type	Country
Maria Fantappiè	lead	CREA	Public research	Italy
Chiara Piccini	member	CREA	Public research	Italy
Panagiotis Tziachris	member	ELGO	Public research	Greece
Vassilis Aschonitis	member	ELGO	Public research	Greece
Gitanjali Thakur	member	UL	Academia	Luxembourg
Fenny van Egmond	member	WR	Public research	Netherlands
Hui Xu	member	ILVO	Public research	Belgium
Arthur Monhonval	member	Soil Capital	Private company	Belgium
Pierre Philippe Claude	member	Polyor	Private company	France
Greta Formaglio	member	eAgronom	Private company	Czech Republic
Kathi Shleidt	observer	Datacove	Private company	Switzerland
Sofia Biffi	observer	AARHUS	Public research	Denmark
Giovanni L'Abate	observer	CREA	Public research	Italy
Andrea Lachi	observer	CREA	Public research	Italy
Paul van Genuchten	observer	WR	Public research	Netherlands
Tommy D'Hose	observer	ILVO	Public research	Belgium
Christine Le Bas	observer	INRAE	Public research	France
Antonio Bispo	observer	INRAE	Public research	France

3. Key discussion points

3.1 Standardisation and harmonisation of data used in the carbon farming systems

The quality of the data used for quantification is essential to achieve a reliable quantification of carbon storage in soil. In the carbon certification framework, the data needed belongs to different domains: soil, vegetation, agriculture, land use and management, water, climate, and so on (figure 3.1)

Figure 3.1 Schematic representation of an MRV system (Smith et al., 2019)

For all those domains a great variety of definitions, codifications and procedures are adopted. In an effort to enable data exchange, several standards have been developed in the last decades, and legislative frameworks have been elaborated, such as INSPIRE for Europe (Directive 2007/2/EC). A further difficulty in Europe arises from the numerous languages spoken in a relatively very small territory.

A large amount of data is collected in Europe, both by private companies and by public bodies, working to support farming systems. The combined used of those data could enable the development of highly representative datasets, which could be used in MRV systems, but the combination is possible only if the data is harmonised.

It is important to underline here the difference between the concepts of standardisation and harmonisation (figure 3.2). Both the standardisation and the harmonisation steps are needed to enable the combined use of datasets of different sources.

Figure 3.2 Visual representation of the concepts of standardisation and harmonisation

We define the standardisation step as the description of the data using agreed (standard) definition, agreed (standard) structure, formats, which are explicitly and in detailed declared in the metadata, so that, any user different from the data producer is enabled in the usage of the data, with theoretically no error (given by a misinterpretation of the data itself). The standards to be declared explicitly in the metadata include (figure 3.3): the sampling design strategy, the sampling protocols, the laboratory analytical procedure, the environmental boundary conditions, and a detailed description of the methodology implemented for the data elaboration.

We define the harmonisation step in the conversion of data, of the same entity (e.g. soil organic carbon), but collected and stored with different standards, to a common unique standard, taken as a reference. The harmonisation step could consist only in a unit of measure conversion, which do not imply an error (if the conversion factor applied is the correct one), or in a conversion function or formula, e.g. if the data is produced with different procedures, which implies the presence of a conversion error, or in a correspondence of terminology, which could imply the it is not available an exact correspondence of terms (e.g. between land management classes, or land use classes, which are defined differently among different standards). The quality of the harmonisation step strongly depends on the quality of the standardisation: a detailed

standardisation, which enables the fully knowledge of the data, together with the availability of conversion formulas or correspondence matrices among concepts and terminologies, could effectively enable the harmonisation. The errors given by the harmonisation process should always be declared for transparency, and the error propagation should be analysed and declared.

We must underline here that, whereas standardisation is always possible, it is not always possible to achieve an harmonisation with acceptable level of ‘harmonisation error’. Therefore, the adoption of common standards should be desirable to avoid the harmonisation step.

Figure 3.3 Components of an MRV system for which the adopted standard should be declared

The focus group has listed several ongoing initiatives for data standardisation.

1. **WoSIS – World Soil Information Service: WoSIS, developed by ISRIC – World Soil Information, aims to standardize and harmonize global soil data.** The service compiles soil profile data from diverse sources, applies consistent quality control procedures, and makes the standardized data accessible to users worldwide. The process involves rigorous evaluation and standardization of soil analytical method

descriptions to ensure data comparability. (<https://www.isric.org/explore/wosis>, <https://www.soilgrids.org/>)

2. **GloSIS – The Global Soil Information System:** Established by the Global Soil Partnership (GSP) under the umbrella of FAO, GloSIS aims to develop a comprehensive ontology for soil data, facilitating data sharing and integration on a global scale. By employing Semantic Web standards, GloSIS enhances the discovery, exploration, and access of soil data, promoting interoperability among diverse soil information systems. (<https://www.fao.org/global-soil-partnership/areas-of-work/soil-information-and-data/en/>, <https://data.apps.fao.org/gloasis/?lang=en>)
3. **EcoDataCube – Open Environmental Data Cube Europe:** EcoDataCube is an open-source spatio-temporal asset catalog for European-wide layers. It was designed to harmonize diverse datasets of various environmental parameters associated to soil, climate, land uses, satellite data, topography etc. at European scale. It was funded by Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) Telecom project 2018-EU-IA-0095 of EU. (<https://stac.ecodatacube.eu>)
4. **SoDaH – The Soils Data Harmonization Database:** SoDaH is an open-source database designed to harmonize diverse soil organic matter (SOM) datasets from multiple research networks. It integrates various datasets into a unified framework, facilitating cross-study comparisons and meta-analyses. This harmonization effort supports a more comprehensive understanding of soil organic matter dynamics across different ecosystems. (https://essd.copernicus.org/articles/13/1843/2021/?utm_source=chatgpt.com) (<https://portal.edirepository.org/nis/metadataviewer?packageid=edi.521.1>)
5. **SoilDataIE Initiative:** The Open Geospatial Consortium's (OGC) Soil Data Interoperability Experiment (SoilDataIE) focuses on advancing geospatial standards for soil data interoperability and analysis. This initiative aims to enhance the sharing and integration of soil data across different platforms by developing and promoting standardized geospatial data models and services. (<https://www.ogc.org/initiatives/soildataie/>)
6. **EJP SOIL:** The working package 6 of the European Joint Programme Soil H2020 project (GA number 862695) has worked towards the standardisation and harmonisation of soil data in Europe, with the purpose to enable and facilitate the implementation of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data principles

(<https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-data/>). Among the relevant deliveries of EJP SOIL we can list: the EJP SOIL metadata catalogue (<https://catalogue.ejpsoil.eu/>), the template for the INSPIRE Soil theme in geopackage format, INSPIRE-SO geopackage (Lachi et al., 2026, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18246825>), the cookbook on soil data assimilation (wiki) (van Genuchten, 2022. <https://ejpsoil.github.io/soildata-assimilation-guidance/>). The initiative has been concluded but has been inherited by the ongoing project Soilwise.

Soilwise: The project Soilwise financed by the European Commission under the Soil Mission (GA number 101112838) is an ongoing project (<https://soilwise-he.eu/>) aimed at providing an integrated and actionable access point to scattered and heterogeneous soil data and knowledge in Europe, making them FAIR and improve trust, willingness, and ability to share and re-use soil data and knowledge. SoilWise applies infrastructure thinking instead of project thinking to design a repository for at least a decade to support European Soil Observatory ([EUSO](#)) evolution accordingly. Soilwise has inherited and is revising the EJP SOIL catalogue, delivering the Soilwise metadata catalogue (<https://soilwise-he.eu/repository/>), revising the template for the INSPIRE Soil theme in Geopackage format, INSPIRE-SO Geopackage and delivering the SoilGeopackage, <https://github.com/soilwise-he/Geopackage-so>, delivering the SoilVoc, soil vocabulary, <https://soilwise-he.github.io/soil-vocabs/>, delivering the SoilCompanion, <https://soil-companion.containers.wur.nl/app/index.html>, and SoilHealthKnowledgeGraph, <https://agroportal.lirmm.fr/ontologies/SHKG>.

3.2 Enabling soil data sharing.

An EU-coherent Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) system needs the development of agreed rules for data sharing among public and private sectors, together with open access tools and procedures enabling for the standardisation and harmonisation of data. The following principles are recognised as essential to promote data sharing: collecting once and using for multiple purposes, respecting personal data privacy, defining and agreeing on the data re-use, giving a service back, and rewarding intellectual property rights. The environmental data collected by public entities in Europe is regulated by a Regulatory Framework which is summarised in the box below. Further details can be found in the “Report on the national and EU regulations on agricultural soil data sharing and national monitoring activities”. (Fantappiè et al., 2021).

Regulatory framework for public data on the environment.

Directive 2003/04/EC on public access to environmental information • EU Accounts Modernisation Directive 2003 and Transparency Directive 2004 • Directive 2003/98/EC on the re-use of public sector information • Directive 2007/2/EC — Infrastructure for Spatial Information (INSPIRE), that aims to promote public access to spatial and infrastructure data that may impact on the environment • Directive 2010/75/EU on industrial emissions (IED) • Directive 2014/95/EU on non-financial reporting including the disclosure of policies on environmental, social and other matters by large undertakings and groups • Directive (EU) 2016/2284 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2016 on the reduction of national emissions of certain atmospheric pollutants amending Directive 2003/35/EC for public participation relating to environment plans and programmes • Directive 1024/2019/EC on open data and re-use of public sector information, known as the Open Data Directive • Directive 2854/2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data, amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Data Act) • Regulation 3012/2024, The Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation.

4. Roadmap of solutions

4.1 Inventory of existing components for standardisation and harmonisation of soil data

4.1.1 Data Formats for Soil Information

The European soil information landscape requires interoperable data formats that accommodate both legacy systems and cloud-native infrastructures while ensuring compliance with INSPIRE and ISO regulatory requirements (European Commission, 2024; International Organization for Standardization [ISO], 2013). Vector geospatial soil data are primarily exchanged using ISO 19136-compliant Geography Markup Language (GML) for INSPIRE reporting and OGC GeoPackage (version 1.4) (ISO, 2020; Open Geospatial Consortium, 2024) for operational workflows. What makes GeoPackage so effective is its SQLite-based portability and seamless integration with field tools. Nevertheless, many workflows still rely on legacy spatial formats like ESRI Shapefiles.

Emerging cloud-optimised formats such as GeoParquet (version 1.1.0+p1, released June 2024) (GeoParquet Contributors, 2024) represent promising developments for large-scale soil vector analytics through columnar storage and efficient subsetting capabilities. Users' reports suggest potential performance advantages (Holmes, 2023; Middleton & Di, 2025), though comprehensive peer-reviewed benchmarks remain limited. For raster and multidimensional datasets, NetCDF-4/HDF5 remains the most common format for long-term scientific archives, while Zarr version 3 specification facilitates cloud-native access to digital soil mapping time-series through chunked, compressed object storage compatible with distributed computing (Rew et al., 2008; Zarr Developers, 2023).

Semantic interoperability is increasingly relying on JSON-LD 1.1 (Sporny et al., 2020) and RDF/Turtle serialisations (Miles & Bechhofer, 2009), enabling soil data to participate in the Linked Open Data ecosystem. GeoJSON (RFC 7946) (Butler et al., 2016) and JSON-LD (W3C) (Sporny et al., 2020) are distinct specifications that can be combined for linked-data applications. However, they are actually separate tools with different jobs, so it's important not to confuse the two. GeoJSON-based web APIs can be extended with JSON-LD contexts to provide semantic capabilities while maintaining backward compatibility

with conventional geospatial clients. A summary of data formats is reported in table 4.1.1.

Table 4.1.1. Data Formats for Soil Information

Format Category	Standard	Status 2026	Primary Use Case	Cloud-Native	Semantic Capability
GeoParquet	Apache (2024)	Emerging Standard	Big Data Analytics	Yes	Medium
GeoPackage	OGC 1.4 (2024)	Active Standard	Data Exchange, Field Apps	Partial	Medium
GeoJSON	RFC 7946 (IETF)	Active Standard	Web APIs	No	Medium
JSON-LD	W3C (2020)	Active Standard	Linked Data	No	High
Shapefile	ESRI (1990s)	Deprecated	Legacy Migration	No	None
GML	ISO 19136 (2007)	Regulatory Only	INSPIRE Compliance	No	High
KML	Google (2006)	Deprecated	Visualization Only	No	Low
Zarr	V3 (2023)	Emerging Standard	DSM Time-Series	Yes	Low
NetCDF-4/HDF5	UCAR/NASA (2008)	Active Standard	Scientific Grids	Partial	High
GeoTIFF	OGC (1992)	Active Standard	Imagery, Static Maps	No	Low
COG	OGC Profile (2019)	Active Standard	Static Soil Maps	Yes	Low
ASCII Grid	ArcInfo (1980s)	Deprecated	Legacy Archive	No	None
NetCDF-3/HDF4	UCAR/NASA (1990s)	Deprecated	Legacy Archive	No	Low
COPC	OGC (2021)	Active Standard	LiDAR, Cloud Access	Yes	Low
LAS/LAZ	ASPRS (1994)	Legacy Standard	LiDAR Exchange	No	Low
CSV + WKT	RFC 4180 (2005)	Active Standard	Field Data, Simple Exchange	No	Low
JSON	RFC 8259 (2017)	Active Standard	REST APIs, Modern Apps	No	Medium
XML (ISO 28258)	ISO 19136 (2007)	Active Standard	Formal Data Exchange	No	High
Excel (.xlsx)	ECMA-376 (2006)	Discouraged	Provisional Storage	No	None
RDF/Turtle	W3C (2004/2019156)	Active Standard	Linked Data, Ontologies	No	Very High
JSON-LD	W3C (2020)	Active Standard	Web Linked Data	No	Very High

4.1.2 Data Structures and Domain Models

Harmonisation of heterogeneous soil data requires internationally recognised domain models that clearly define entity relationships, observation semantics, and classification system mappings. Without this formal structure, automated data integration remains computationally unreachable. ISO 28258:2013 (ISO, 2013) provides the essential blueprint for sharing digital soil data by defining feature types (Site, Plot, Profile) based on the ISO 19156 Observations and Measurements framework (ISO, 2023). Most importantly, it's flexible enough to work with diverse national description methodologies through flexible encoding rules and external code list references.

Within the European Union, INSPIRE soil version 3.0 (European Commission, 2024) takes ISO 19156 principles and turns them into legally mandated UML/GML schemas. By defining harmonised object types (SoilBody, SoilProfile, ProfileElement) this framework allows cross-border soil quality reporting and monitoring as long as the countries have implemented the required INSPIRE schema and code-list mappings. In INSPIRE the soil properties are modelled using O&M standard of OGC. OGC also support the standards SensorThing API, which extend the possibility to store large amount of data as collected by sensors.

GeoSciML facilitates interdisciplinary data exchange across Earth sciences. Governed by the OGC and IUGS since 2005, it operates as a hybrid domain model structured using UML/XML schemas. This framework is explicitly designed to support the cross-domain integration of geology and soil datasets, providing a medium semantic approach to scientific interoperability (Open Geospatial Consortium, 2017). A summary of data structures and domain models is reported in table 4.1.2.

Table 4.1.2 Data Structures and Domain Models

Model/Standard	Authority	Domain Scope	Structure Type	Semantic	Primary Use
ISO 28258:2013	ISO TC 190	Global Soil Science	Hierarchical (O&M)	Medium	International Exchange
INSPIRE Soil v3.0	EC/JRC	EU Regulatory	UML/GML	Medium	EU Legal Compliance
GeoSciML	OGC/IUGS	Geology/Soil	UML/XML	Medium	Cross-domain Integration
O&M	ISO/OGC	Cross-domain observations	UML/XML	Medium	

OGC SensorThings API	OGC	Cross-domain observations	REST/JSON	Medium	Cross- domain Integration
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4.1.3 Vocabularies and Controlled Terminologies

Getting multilingual European soil databases to work together depends on having a common set of definitions. By using these standard vocabularies, we can give every data point a clear, unique identifier. This makes it possible to search across languages and ensures that all our metadata is indexed the same way across the continent. AGROVOC, maintained by the Food and Agriculture Organization, constitutes the primary multilingual thesaurus for agricultural and environmental domains. As described in Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO, 2026) documentation, it encompasses around 40,000 concepts in over 40 languages and is published as a SKOS-XL concept scheme with dereferenceable URIs enabling direct integration into semantic soil databases (Miles & Bechhofer, 2009).

The General Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus (GEMET) version 4.2.3 (European Environment Agency, 2021), developed by the European Environment Agency and mandatory for INSPIRE metadata keyword annotation, provides over 6,000 environmental concepts in 25 languages, including specialized soil-related terminology such as soil erosion, soil contamination, and soil organic matter

The GloSIS ontology (Palma et al., 2025) includes detailed code lists that act like a master dictionary for soil layers, textures, and lab tests. By using the W3C Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS) recommendation (Miles & Bechhofer, 2009), these lists help computers automatically "read" and align different datasets, making the entire system much smarter and more connected.

DATA4C+ is a domain thesaurus that standardises terminology for 224 management practices affecting soil organic carbon (SOC) storage in agriculture and forestry. It structures them hierarchically according to key drivers of SOC change and supports the consistent labeling of experimental data and meta-analyses on carbon sequestration practices (Fujisaki et al., 2023). ISO 11074:2025 provides a reference vocabulary for soil quality, defining hundreds of terms that cover general soil concepts, soil description, sampling, risk assessment, remediation and ecotoxicology, and supports the consistent use of terminology across ISO soil standards and national implementations (ISO, 2025).

The Soil Food Web Ontology (SFWO) is an OWL ontology that provides a structure for trophic interactions, diets and feeding processes of soil biota, offering a logically consistent vocabulary to standardise trophic trait datasets and support automated soil food web reconstruction and semantic querying in soil ecology (Le Guillarme et al., 2023). The emerging Soil Health Vocabulary, developed as part of the Soil Health Knowledge Graph within the SoilWISE initiative (Wang, 2025) contributes a focused set of soil health concepts (e.g., indicators, processes, management levers) that are being integrated into a soil health knowledge graph to align diverse definitions and support interoperable description of soil health status and EU Mission Soil monitoring needs.

The INRAE Thesaurus (INRAE, 2021) is an open, multilingual controlled vocabulary maintained by INRAE that covers agriculture, food and environmental sciences, with more than 16,000 concepts structured into thematic domains and microthesauri, including soil-related terms. Published in SKOS-XL with stable URIs and mappings to resources such as AGROVOC, it is used to index and annotate INRAE publications and datasets, supporting semantic interoperability and cross-language search. A summary of data vocabularies is reported in table 4.1.3.

Table 4.1.3. *Vocabularies and Controlled Terminologies*

Vocabulary	Authority	Languages	Concepts	Domain	Role
AGROVOC	FAO	42	40,000+	Agriculture/Environment	Multilingual Bridge
GEMET	EAA/EIONET	25+	6,000+	Environmental Policy	EU Regulatory
GloSIS Code Lists	FAO/ISRIC	6+	2,000–3,000	Pedology	Semantic Standard
ISO 11074:2025	ISO	3	1,000+	Soil Science	Reference Standard
DATA4C+	EU Projects	English	224 (est.)	SOC Management	Carbon Farming
Soil Health Knowledge Graph (SHKG)	Wageningen University & Research / SoilWISE HE	English (Extensible)	1,800 (est.)	Soil Health	Knowledge discovery system
SFWO	Community	English	1000 (est.)	Soil Ecology	Biological Domain
INRAE Thesaurus	INRAE	French/English	16,000+	Agriculture/Environment/Food	Institutional Semantic Standard

4.1.4 Ontologies and Formal Knowledge Representations

To enable the seamless integration and interpretation of diverse environmental data related to soil, ontologies and formal knowledge representations provide the essential

semantic foundation for technical interoperability. Modern soil data systems in Europe are built using a layered approach to organize information. At the heart of this structure is the GloSIS Web Ontology (Palma et al., 2025), which serves as a leading semantic blueprint for making soil data consistent and compatible all over the world. GloSIS puts soil standards (like ISO 28258 and INSPIRE Soil) into action by turning them into a smart, machine-readable framework. With more than 300 categories built on standard web languages, it connects scattered soil databases into one network. This allows researchers to run a single search across many different systems at once, even if those systems weren't originally designed to work together.

SOSA/SSN (Semantic Sensor Network Ontology; World Wide Web Consortium, 2017) provides a lightweight core (SOSA) and extended framework (SSN) for modelling sensors, observations, actuators, and sampling activities, designed as a modular architecture supporting IoT, geoinformatics, and scientific monitoring. QUDT (Quantities, Units, Dimensions and Types; Hodgson et al., 2014), developed initially by NASA, set the rules for physical quantities, units of measure, and dimensional analysis in OWL, enabling automated unit conversion and dimensional validation across measurement systems. GeoSPARQL (Open Geospatial Consortium, 2012) extends SPARQL with spatial query functions and topological relations (RCC8, DE-9IM) for querying geospatial RDF data, providing the geometric and topological vocabulary for soil spatial features. PROV-O (Lebo et al., 2013) expresses the W3C PROV Data Model in OWL2, defining classes and properties for representing provenance chains (entities, activities, and agents) that are essential for tracking data lineage, transformations, and quality assessments in soil information workflows. SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System; Miles & Bechhofer, 2009) provides a lightweight RDF vocabulary for controlled vocabularies, thesauri, and classification schemes, enabling hierarchical concept relationships and multilingual labels for soil classification systems and code lists.

ISO 28258 and INSPIRE Soil, originally specified as UML/GML schemas, have been expressed as OWL representations to serve as semantic "bridges" aligning XML/GML and relational implementations with GloSIS. The semantic layer provided by these ontologies can be interfaced with physical data storage through Ontology-Based Data Access (OBDA) middleware, which dynamically maps relational database schemas (e.g., PostgreSQL/PostGIS implementations) to the OWL framework, allowing SPARQL queries

to be automatically translated to SQL. In operational pipelines, R2RML (Das et al., 2012) and related mapping languages enable the generation of RDF graphs from existing implementations, creating queryable SPARQL endpoints that can be linked to external vocabularies such as AGROVOC and GEMET.

Emerging soil-specific ontologies extend the semantic infrastructure into specialised domains. The SoilWISE Ontology (SoilWISE Consortium, 2024) supports the EU SoilWISE knowledge graph, integrating metadata about datasets, organisations, repositories, and soil health indicators, with active development of a Soil Health Knowledge Graph comprising over 10,996 RDF triples linking to AGROVOC, GloSIS, ISO 11074:2025, and GEMET vocabularies. The Soil Food Web Ontology (SFWO) provides standardised terminology and logical formalisation for soil trophic ecology, harmonising definitions of trophic groups, feeding processes, and dietary traits across taxonomic groups to support trophic trait dataset standardisation, knowledge graph construction, and automated soil food web reconstruction using OWL reasoning. Ontology governance within the soil information community increasingly emphasises persistent HTTP URIs, formal term deprecation policies, and machine-readable metadata. These practices are evident in GloSIS documentation and the SoilWISE infrastructure to ensure that soil knowledge graphs remain stable integration points for Member State infrastructures and Mission Soil-related initiatives. A summary of Ontologies and Formal Knowledge Representations is reported in table 4.1.4.

Table 4.1.4. *Ontologies and Formal Knowledge Representations*

Ontology	Authority	KR Form	Reasoning	Application	Scope
GloSIS OWL	FAO	OWL 2 DL, >300 classes	High (classification)	Global soil harmonisation	Soil domain
ISO 28258 OWL	ISO TC 190	OWL (medium)	Medium (validation)	Digital soil exchange	Soil structures
INSPIRE Soil OWL	EC/INSPIRE	OWL (medium)	Low–medium	EU soil reporting	EU harmonisation
SOSA/SSN	W3C/OGC	OWL profiles	Low–medium	Observation modelling	Cross-domain
QUDT	QUDT/NASA	OWL (medium)	Low–medium	Units, quantities	Cross-domain
GeoSPARQL	OGC	OWL/RDFS + SPARQL	Medium (spatial)	Spatial queries	Geospatial RDF
PROV-O	W3C	OWL (medium)	Low–medium	Provenance tracking	Cross-domain
SKOS/SKOS- XL	W3C	SKOS (low)	Low (hierarchical)	Controlled vocabularies	Cross-domain

SoilWISE Ontology	SoilWISE	OWL (medium–high)	Medium–high	Knowledge graph	Soil metadata
SFWO	Community	OWL (medium)	Medium (trophic)	Soil biota modelling	Soil ecology

4.1.5 Conversion Tools and Harmonisation Pipelines

End-to-end harmonisation workflows in European soil infrastructures typically combine schema-aware ETL tools, geospatial format converters and semantic mapping components to migrate legacy holdings into ISO/INSPIRE-compliant and GloSIS-aligned representations.

Hale Studio (Wetransform, 2026), FME (Safe Software, 2026), and GDAL/OGR (GDAL/OGR Contributors, 2024) are used to normalize coordinate reference systems, convert Shapefile, ASCII Grid and proprietary database structures into GeoPackage, COG or Zarr, and enforce INSPIRE Soil schemas prior to loading into ISO 28258-based relational back-ends (GDAL/OGR Contributors, 2024).

On the semantic layer, R2RML-based converters such as GeoTriples (Kyzirakos et al., 2014) and dedicated vocabulary tools such as VocBench 3 (Stellato et al., 2020) apply mappings expressed in SSSOM (Matentzoglou et al., 2022) or OWL to attach GloSIS classes, SKOS concepts and provenance annotations, thereby turning structurally harmonised datasets into interoperable knowledge-graph resources that can be reused across projects and jurisdictions. A summary of Conversion Tools and Harmonisation Pipelines is reported in table 4.1.5.

Table 4.1.5. Conversion Tools and Harmonisation Pipelines

Tool	Vendor/Community	Function	Input Formats	Output Formats	Context
Hale Studio	wetransform (OSS)	Schema Mapping	DB, Shapefile, GML	GML, GeoPackage	INSPIRE Compliance
FME	Safe Software	Enterprise ETL	400+ formats	Multiple	Enterprise Transform.
GDAL/OGR	OSGeo (OSS)	Format Translation	200+ formats	Multiple	Foundational Library
GeoTriples	Community (OSS)	RDF Conversion	SQL, Shapefile	RDF/Turtle	Linked Data Creation
VocBench3	FAO (OSS)	Vocabulary Mgmt	SKOS, OWL	Multiple	Vocab. Maintenance

4.2 Results of the session at the carbon farming summit 19th March 2026 in Padua.

During the carbon farming summit in Padua, on Thursday 19th March 2026, a parallel session was held on Data Standardisation and Harmonisation towards Credible MRV systems. The session was promoted by the focus group 3.1 of CREDIBLE, in collaboration with focus group 3.4, and with [MARVIC](#), [MRV4SOC](#), [Soilwise](#), and [CAFAMORE](#) projects.

4.2.1 Session contents:

Tier 3 model-based Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification systems require a large number of input data to calibrate, run and validate the applied models. The efficient and accurate sharing and use of those data requires systematic collection and storage, applying standard formats and vocabularies and aggregation or disaggregation at appropriate scales. Standardisation is at the basis of reusability, which is one of the FAIR principles, towards making data FAIR, that is, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Standardisation is a prerequisite for interoperability and harmonisation, that is, those procedures which eventually can permit to minimize the errors, in case data collected with different standards is combined. MRV systems require data of soil, land use and management, and climate, as well as collected using different data collection techniques (in field, lab, remote sensing). The different domains require different standards and tooling, developed and maintained by different groups.

The session presented recent advancements and best practices, with introductory presentations by experts covering MRV data assessment, benchmark sites, sampling design, and the operationalisation of standardised vocabularies. Participants was engaged in a mentimeter session and in breakout groups to discuss challenges and co-develop solutions. The session aimed to foster interaction among stakeholders and advance the alignment of standards and tools, supporting more reliable, efficient, and interoperable MRV systems for carbon and soil monitoring.

Topics addressed by the session:

- ✓ Integrating value chains
- ✓ Advancing MRV systems
- ✓ Data and reporting coherence
- ✓ Clarifying carbon claims
- ✓ Innovation and new opportunities

Keywords: standardisation, harmonisation, FAIR principles, vocabularies, metadata, soil, farm management data, keywords, ontologies, transfer functions, tools and formats, sampling.

Speakers and chair

The speakers and chair of the session (fig. 4.2.1) were:

- Chair: Dr. Maria Fantappiè, (CREDIBLE, MRV4SOC, Soilwise) Senior Researcher at Council for Agricultural Research and Economics - Agriculture and Environment (CREA-AA).

- Speakers:

Dr. Hui Xu, MARVIC project manager, Researcher at Flanders research institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO)

Dr. Sofia Biffi, Postdoc researcher at Aarhus University

Dr. Fenny van Egmond, MARVIC/SoilWise/CAFAMORE, Wageningen Environmental Research (WENR) and ISRIC – World Soil Information

- Support:

Panagiotis Tziachris (SWRI), Gitanjali Thakur (LCSES, UniLu), Greta Formaglio (EAGRONOM), Chiara Piccini (CREA-AA), Pierre Philippe Claude (Polyor).

Session agenda

Introductory presentations (60 minutes)

MENTIMETER session (15 minutes)

Breakout groups (15 minutes)

Figure 4.2.1 Organisers (speakers and supporters) of the session E11. Data Standardisation and Harmonisation towards Credible MRV systems participants, on Thursday 19th March 2026 at the Antenore Room, European Carbon Farming Summit, Padua, Italy, organisers (speakers and supporters) from the left to the right: Pierre Philippe Claude, Maria Fantappiè, Panagiotis Tziachris, Sofia Biffi, Hui Xu, Fenny van Egmond, Gitanjali Thakur.

Promotion of the session and participants

An email was sent by Maria Fantappiè to all the participants registered to the Carbon Farming Summit who had shared their email contact (about 600 emails sent), with a registration form online. A promotion was also done on LinkedIn by Gitanjali Thakur.

The registration form was compiled by 106, and the final attendees (fig. 4.2.2) to the session were 44 (organisers excluded), distributed among the stakeholders' categories reported in the table 4.2.1.

Table 4.2.1 Participants to the session E11, on Thursday 19th March 2026 at the European Carbon Summit in Padua, Italy

Stakeholders' categories	Registered	Attending
Research and academia	31	17
Intermediaries (Advisory and extension services, certifiers, consultancy, service provider)	34	6
IT support (including MRV technologies, RS, modeling)	11	7
Supply chain actor (input and output)	9	3
Carbon Project Developer	7	6
Farmers and farmers union	7	3
Credit buyers and project funders	4	0
Regulators and policymakers, public entities	3	2
TOTAL	106	44

Figure 4.2.2 Session E11. Data Standardisation and Harmonisation towards Credible MRV systems participants, on Thursday 19th March 2026 at the Antenore Room, European Carbon Farming Summit, Padua, Italy.

4.2.1 Session results

4.2.1.1 Introductory presentations

All the slides presented by the 4 speakers are available on zenodo (Fantappiè et al., 2026, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19230942>).

Dr. Maria Fantappiè introduced on to the topic of data standardisation and harmonisation for MRV systems.

The introduction tackled the following topics:

- the concept of MRV systems and the data needed for their implementation; a visual introduction to the concepts of data standardisation and data harmonisation;
- the diversity in the implementation of MRV systems in terms of sampling design, sampling protocols, measure and re-measure approach, measure and model approach, different kinds of models for crops, and SOC/N, different analytical procedures used for the same soil properties, and/or the usage of transfer/pedo-transfer functions, the variation in boundary conditions in space and in time (climate, management, and so on) which determines varying boundary conditions for the same baseline condition for soil management (baseline conditions varying in space and time);
- a visual introduction to the concepts of data-structure models for different data domains, and the respective availability of different standards (e.g. INSPIRE, SensorThings, O&M, and so on), and different vocabularies for data domains (e.g. AGROVOC, GEMET, GLOSIS, and soon);
- a proposed solution to combine the INSPIRE soil standard data model with standard soil vocabularies undertaken in EJP SOIL project (Lachi et al., 2026) and now under update under Soilwise project.

Dr. Hui Xu presented an example of implementation of Metadata Catalogue & Farm Data Assessment as released by MARVIC project.

The presentation talked the functioning of the [MARVIC metadata catalogue](#) in terms of compilation procedure, filtering tool, software used, metadata standardisation, storage (in zenodo) and harvesting by Soilwise.

The presentation talked also the topic of farm data assessment, with the example of the [DJUSTCONNECT portal](#) produced by [ILVO](#) and enlarged in the [CEADS](#) portal (Common European Agricultural Data Space).

Dr. Sofia Biffi introduced on the topic of benchmark sites: their use, design and requirements. She has presented the concept of benchmark site, defined as *reference location where soil, plant, carbon fluxes, activity data and environmental data are collected under known conditions*. They are used to compare SOC stock changes and other carbon budget components (e.g., biomass, CO₂ fluxes) against business-as-usual baselines and to validate modelled predictions. It is recommended to have an umbrella of benchmark sites, covering multiple site types, that is, pedolandsapes, with data collected across different time periods and spatial scales. Different kind of benchmark sites were presented, together with their pros and cons: national soil monitoring networks, long-term and short-term experiments, flux tower networks, on-farm monitoring networks, living-labs. She underlined the key challenge is the standardisation and harmonisation of data collected in those benchmark sites.

Dr. Fenny van Egmond introduced on the topic of standardised vocabularies for MRV systems. Standard vocabularies are structured, hierarchical, and inter-linked terms of specific domains, which are defined and maintained by bodies, which officially detain the knowledge on those specific domains, and are findable online. In a standard vocabulary each term is permanently accessible through a link, e.g. by a URL (Uniform Resource Locator). She presented several standard vocabularies which are currently available to be used in MRV systems. Examples of standard vocabularies were given, such as: agrovoc, <https://agrovoc.fao.org/browse/agrovoc/en/>, gemet, <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/gemet/en/about/>, glosis, <https://agroportal.lirmm.fr/ontologies/GLOSIS?p=summary>, SoilVoc, <https://soilwise-he.github.io/soil-vocabs/>.

4.2.1.2 Mentimeter session results

A mentimeter session was held consisting of 13 slides, and corresponding questions. The list of questions and share of answering/not-answering session attendees is reported in the table 4.2.2.

Table 4.2.2 Mentimeter questions and share of answering/not-answering session attendees.

Questions	Answering	Not-answering
1) Which country are you from?	41	3
2) To which stakeholder category do you belong?	38	6
3) Which kind of data do you currently use in an MRV system?	37	7
4) Which model for crop and/or carbon modeling do you know/use?	34	10
5) Which data-format do you currently use for soil and/or carbon-related data?	31	13
6) Which data-model standards do you know/use?	21	23
7) Which standard vocabularies do you know/use?	19	25
8) Which are the biggest challenges for standardisation?	27	17
9) Do you know any more initiative on data standardisation, and especially for MRV systems?	17	27
10) Which are the biggest challenges for harmonisation?	23	21
11) Do you know any more initiative on data harmonisation, and especially for MRV systems?	15	29
12) Do you agree that standardised/harmonised MRV systems could produce higher valuable/credible carbon credits?	32	12
13) What is still needed to implement standardised and harmonised MRV systems?	26	18

The first questions were thought to understand the composition of session attendees. As expected, since the summit was held in Italy, most of the participants were from Italy, but a wide representativeness of other European countries was present at the session as depicted in the figure 4.2.3. In decreasing order, the other participants were from: Germany, France, Greece, Finland, Spain, Switzerland, Belgium, Czech Republic, Austria, Ireland, Denmark, Portugal, Hungary, Netherlands, Scotland.

As for the stakeholder categories of session attendees, they are reported in table 4.2.1 and figure 4.2.4. Research and academia category was the most represented. Credit buyers were not present at the session. Policy makers, farmers and supply chain actors were the less represented. The service sector supporting the MRV systems and carbon farming implementation were good represented: farm advisors, certification bodies, auditors, IT companies.

Figure 4.2.3 Cloud of answers to the question “which country are you from?”

Figure 4.2.4 Closed-option list question “to which stakeholder category do you belong?”

The further 3 were general technical questions, to which a high share of attendees responded (> 70%). The cloud of answers to the questions on kind of data used in MRV systems (fig. 4.2.5) revealed that the most used data were remote sensing data, followed by farm data, soil data and meteorological data. Although described differently, most of the other datasets indicated in the cloud of answer could be assigned to those great categories. Other categories less represented were related to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and emission factors, above ground biomass, proximal sensing, and national monitoring. The cloud of answers to the questions on crop and/or carbon models known/used (fig. 4.2.6) revealed that the most used model was RothC, followed by armosa, dndc, daycent, cool-farm, allometric models, epic, agricarbon-eo,

Figure 4.2.6 Cloud of answers to the question “Which model for crop and/or carbon modelling do you know/use?”

Figure 4.2.7 Cloud of answers to the question “Which data-format do you currently use for soil and/or carbon-related data?”

The following 6 technical questions received a share of answers ranging from the 34% to the 61% of attendees. Only half of the attendees answered to the question on data-model standards (fig. 4.2.8), and the majority of respondent gave none as an answer, or other inconsistent and off-topic answers, testifying that the concept of data-model standard was almost unknown. Only few of the respondent answered that the known/used data-model standards were INSPIRE and ISO 28258. Even less attendees responded to the question on standard vocabularies (fig. 4.2.9), and the most of them gave none as an answer. Duden, a physical vocabulary of German language was given as an answer. Then a joke was done with “donald duck”. Again, ICOS and ISO were indicated

as an answer testifying their relevance in the standardisation process, although none of them is a standard vocabulary. Finally, only agrovoc was known/used as standard vocabulary.

Figure 4.2.8 Cloud of answers to the question “Which data-model standards do you know/use?”

Figure 4.2.9 Cloud of answers to the question “Which standard vocabularies do you know/use?”

The 61% of the attendees gave an answer to the question on the challenges for standardisation (fig. 4.2.10) which were identified as: lack of knowledge, lack of awareness, the effort, complexity, and cost in the implementation, the fragmentation and lack of consensus, and finally the lack of enforcement. The 52% of the attendees gave an answer to the question on the challenges for harmonisation (fig. 4.2.11), with

similar answers as for standardisation: lack of knowledge and guidelines, the effort, complexity and lack of incentives, the lack of alignment, consensus, varying end-use, the diversity of analytical methods, and subjective interpretation. Some argued for the lack of usefulness.

Figure 4.2.10 Open-ended question “Which are the biggest challenges for standardisation?”

Figure 4.2.11 Open-ended question “Which are the biggest challenges for harmonisation?”

The less answered questions were those on the known initiatives on standardisation (fig. 4.1.12) and harmonisation (fig. 4.1.13), to which only 17 and 15 session attendees answered. Most of the respondents didn’t know about standardisation/harmonisation initiatives. Among the standardisation initiatives the listed ones were [EJPSOIL](#), [BONARES](#), [eLTER](#), [LTER](#), [CEADS](#), [FSDN](#), [LUCAS handbook](#), [VERRA](#) sampling handbooks. It is interesting to notice that [INSPIRE](#), [ICOS](#) and [ISO](#) were not listed. Among the

harmonisation initiatives the most cited ones were [MRV4SOC](#), [MARVIC](#), and again SOILHARMONY. Less known were: [CAFAMORE](#), [ORCASA](#), [ADAPT](#), [Europe-land project](#), [ARD](#), [soil carbon futures](#), and the [Soil Monitoring Law](#) (SML). The recently approved project proposal, SOILHARMONY, not yet started, was indicated both as standardisation and harmonisation initiative.

Figure 4.2.12 Cloud of answers to the question “Do you know any more initiative on data standardisation, and especially for MRV systems?”

Figure 4.2.13 Cloud of answers to the question “Do you know any more initiative on data harmonisation, and especially for MRV systems?”

Finally, 22 over 44 of the attendees (fig. 4.2.14) answered yes to the question “Do you agree that ?”, 8 over 44 answered partially, 2 over 44 answered no idea, and 12 over 44 didn’t answer. No one answered no!

The final question (fig. 4.2.15) was an open question asking for suggestions on what is still needed to implement standardised and harmonised MRV systems, to which 26 over 44 of the attendees answered, giving insightful suggestions, most of which were related to policy needs. The suggestions underlined the need for enforcement, regulations and coordination among the regulations, with a suggested alignment even beyond EU. The suggestions lead to an enforcement towards common standards, decided by a central authority, with a clear governance. Other suggestions lead to the need for more investments and education, and incentives, which could produce awareness on the existence of those standards and stimulate the willingness to adopt them.

Figure 4.2.14 Closed-option list question “Do you agree that standardised/harmonised MRV systems could produce higher valuable/credible carbon credits?”

Figure 4.2.15 Open-ended question “What is still needed to implement standardised and harmonised MRV systems?”

4.2.1.3 Breakout groups discussions results

The participants to the session were divided into 5 round tables, and the following topics were discussed:

- Which is the biggest challenge for data standardisation?
- Which is the biggest challenge for data harmonisation?
- How do users share data?

The following answers were obtained.

1. Which is the biggest challenge for data standardization?

For data standardization, participants identified several challenges. They stated the absence of clear incentives to invest time and resources in standardization work, alongside persistent difficulties in achieving consensus and effective collaboration across organizations and communities. Respondents also pointed to misaligned temporal scales and timeframes, a general disconnection (systems, actors) and limited traceability of data as factors that complicate efforts to implement and sustain common standards.

2. Which is the biggest challenge for data harmonization?

Regarding data harmonization, participants emphasized that communication and collaboration remain central obstacles, suggesting that social and organizational coordination is as difficult as the technical work itself. In addition, they highlighted the lack or immaturity of tools, protocols, and other practical mechanisms needed to merge datasets, which makes harmonization cumbersome and increases the risk of inconsistencies.

3. How do users share data?

The methods for sharing data range from structured repositories and online catalogues like Zenodo to the use of metadata files and APIs. However, the act of sharing is heavily influenced by external pressures. Private sector participation is often complicated by questions of data ownership and the high costs associated with sharing data or changing existing systems. Additionally, users noted that the significant upfront time and cost required for harmonization is often not accounted for, creating a hidden barrier to effective sharing.

A summary of the challenges and suggestions received from the discussion are reported in the table 4.2.3.

Table 4.2.3 Summary of the challenges and suggestions from the breakout group discussions.

Challenges	Suggestions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● No incentives. ● Match scales of time (timeframes). ● Disconnection of things. ● Traceability of data. ● Lack of collaboration. ● Private sector: who owns the data. ● Cost in data sharing (private sector partners). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Communication, collaboration. ● Tools to merge (protocols). ● Repositories (zenodo). ● Online catalogues ● Files of metadata. ● API. ● Make standards mandatory

4.2.1.4 Final recommendations from the session

The following final recommendations were obtained:

- 1) make it mandatory (e.g. to be included in the current MRV standards, such as VERRA, and the CRCF implementing rules and guiding documents) to use those standards data format, data models, metadata and vocabularies, in order to have certified carbon credits.
- 2) Data standardisation and harmonisation should build on existing protocols like ICOS and eLTER, but many different standards make it difficult for users to know which ones to follow. Clear guidance is needed, ideally through the CRCF, to show which standards align with key policies such as LULUCF, CAP, and CSRD.
- 3) A centralised portal to access to the data could help by supporting data sharing, offering incentives for farmers to monetise their data, and ensuring reliable data through quality checks.
- 4) Additionally, many companies collect large amounts of information without knowing which data is actually valuable for markets or specific use cases, so better guidance on what is needed would be helpful—though motivation to share data remains low until stronger incentives are in place.

4.3 Barriers and incentives for sharing input-data needed in carbon farming and MRV systems in Europe

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To overcome several technical, economic and legal challenges, and towards harmonisation we recommend:

Recommendation 1

Recognising the advantages of a standardised baseline as defined by CRCF, in order to reward early movers, encourage new adopters and simplify additionality tests, the representativeness of the data used is recognised as a core criterion for the establishment of a robust standardised baseline. This should be accompanied by a regular recalibration –to reflect evolving practices and climate trends (Don et al., 2023)– which implies the implementation of an EU-wide system for data sharing, based on EU legislation (see the regulatory framework).

Recommendation 2

Clarification should be given about the concept of baseline to clearly distinguish among baseline for carbon removal in aboveground and belowground biomass, baseline for carbon removal in soil, baseline in greenhouse gases emission reductions.

Recommendation 3

A full implementation of INSPIRE regulation is needed for all types of data needed in the MRV systems –climate data, soil data, greenhouse gases emission data, carbon and nitrogen input data, agricultural and forestry management data, plant phenology data, remote sensing and proximal sensing data– in terms of data model structures, ontologies, sampling protocols and analytical procedures, quality criteria for laboratories, unit of measure, data formats, and their mutual transformation rules and standard procedures to determine the associated uncertainties. The tools and knowledge developed for the INSPIRE implementation should be made freely available

to both public and private users and should be user friendly for both the data owners/holders and the end users.

[Recommendation 4](#)

The following principles are recognised as essential to promote data sharing: i) collecting data once and using them for multiple purposes; ii) confidentiality of personal data; iii) recognising data ownership; iv) defining and agreeing on the data re-use; v) giving a service back; vi) rewarding intellectual property rights. As farm data –including georeferenced soil data– are recognised as personal data (Fantappiè et al., 2021), the confidentiality should be guaranteed by anonymisation/aggregation procedures, or by access/sharing with request procedures, which imply the signing of embedded contracts for data sharing with farmers.

[Recommendation 5](#)

To incentivise private companies to share their data, the effort of data collection should in large part be subsidised with the support of the EU. One farmer should have the ability to request a subsidy for data collection –such as soil sampling– and hire himself a company to perform both sampling and lab analysis. Farmers will be incentivised to share openly their data if a service is given back, such an open system that estimates baselines and SOC storage potential (with associated uncertainty).

[Recommendation 6](#)

The determination of activity-specific baselines by certification companies is an expensive activity, therefore, receiving reliable standardised baseline as a service-back by the EU Commission could be an incentive for data sharing.

5 Conclusion and next steps

The final public session organised by the focus group 3.1 at the 3rd Carbon Farming Summit in summit was quite successful and lead to the conclusion that the main of the attendees agreed that *a standardised/harmonised MRV systems could produce higher valuable/credible carbon credits*. Finding solutions to overcome legal and technical constraints for data sharing is a prerequisite to the determination of accurate and reliable standardised baselines, which could reduce the cost of the carbon certification system, constituting an effective leverage and incentives for data sharing from privates' stakeholders. At the end, although the harmonisation between standards could be possible and available, the final recommendation arising from the focus group activity is to get to an enforcement for common standards to be adopted for the data used in the MRV systems, even beyond EU borders, accompanied by a strong effort in capacity building and awareness raising.

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